

Article

Development of ErbB2-targeting Liposomes for Enhancing Drug Delivery to ErbB2-positive Breast Cancer

Sho Ueno ^{1,#}, Min Woo Kim ^{2,#}, Gibok Lee ³, Yong Il Park ³, Takuro Niidome ^{1,*}, and Ruda Lee ^{2,*}

¹ Faculty of Advanced Science and Technology, Kumamoto University, Kumamoto 860-8555, Japan

² International Research Organization for Advanced Science and Technology (IROAST), Kumamoto University, Kumamoto 860-8555, Japan; nanodream89@gmail.com

³ School of Chemical Engineering, Chonnam National University, Gwangju 61186, Republic of Korea; midcon1@gmail.com, ypark@jnu.ac.kr

These authors have contributed equally to this work

* Correspondence: niidome@kumamoto-u.ac.jp; aeju-lee@kumamoto-u.ac.jp

ErbB2 is a type of receptor tyrosine kinase, which is known to be involved in tumorigenesis, tumor aggressiveness, and clinical outcome. ErbB2-targeting therapy using therapeutic antibodies has been successful in breast cancer treatment. However, the need for repeated treatments and the high cost are major disadvantages with monoclonal antibody therapies. Compared with antibodies, peptides are cheap, very stable for a long time, and have low immunogenicity. We have developed a highly specific cancer-targeting drug delivery system using a targeting peptide to maximize the therapeutic efficiency of rapamycin and to help prevent drug resistance in ErbB2-positive breast cancer. Physicochemical characterization confirmed the successful construction of ErbB2-targeting liposomes (^{ErbB2}Lipo). Comparison of a scrambled peptide (ScrErbB2) with the ErbB2-targeting peptide confirmed that these peptides had similar properties except for the targeting ability. The ^{ErbB2}Lipo exhibited higher delivery efficiency in ErbB2 positive BT-474 cells than non-targeting liposomes conjugated with ScrErbB2 (^{ScrErbB2}Lipo). This peptide-targeting strategy has the potential to improve the efficacy of chemotherapy in ErbB2-positive cancers.

Keywords: targeted therapy; targeting peptide; mTOR inhibitor, immunoliposome, drug delivery system, breast cancer therapy

Table S1. Fmoc determination**> ErbB2 peptide**

Amino acid	Volume[mL]	Abs[-]	mmol	Introduction rate[%]
Arg(Pbf)	14.0	0.799	0.1883	94.15
Lys(boc)	14.0	0.843	0.2080	104.00
Phe	14.0	0.662	0.2049	102.45
Asn(Trt)	14.0	0.558	0.2221	111.05
Ser(tBu)	14.0	0.666	0.2112	105.60
Pro	14.0	0.589	0.2321	116.05
Pro	14.0	0.613	0.2197	109.85

> ScrErbB2 peptide

Amino acid	Volume[mL]	Abs[-]	mmol	Introduction rate[%]
Phe	14.0	1.330	0.2116	105.79
Arg(Pbf)	14.0	1.290	0.2098	104.91
Pro	14.0	1.277	0.2016	100.81
Asn(Trt)	14.0	1.737	0.2098	104.89
Pro	14.0	1.691	0.2307	115.37
Ser(tBu)	14.0	1.439	0.2269	113.46
Lys(boc)	14.0	1.457	0.2028	101.42

Figure S1. Synthetic chemical structure of DSPE-PEG-ErbB2.

Figure S2. MDA-MB-231 and BT-474 cellular level of ErbB2 (185 kDa). GAPDH was used as an internal control (37 kDa).